

Functional Assays for Solute Carrier Transporters

FFN206 based assay for SLC18A1 using HEK-293 SLC18A1 OE cells

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Assay description

FFN206 (FFN= False Fluorescent Neurotransmitter) is a fluorescent assay developed in intact cells for monoamine uptake.

Compound FFN206 is a fluorescent SLC18A1/SLC18A2 substrate which was developed and allowed functional examination of VMAT1 and VMAT2 in cell culture, using fluorescence microscopy or microplate reader (Figure 1).

It crosses the plasma membrane and accumulates into vesicles by SLC18A1 or SLC18A2 transport.

SLC18A1 is a transporter protein expressed on vesicular membranes for the monoamines (dopamine, serotonin, norepinephrine, and histamine). While the SLC18A2 isoform is expressed in the monoaminergic neurons throughout the CNS, the SLC18A1 isoform is only expressed in endocrine/paracrine cells associated with the stomach, intestine, and sympathetic nervous system. It functions as antiporter (2H⁺ out/1 monoamine in) essential for monoamine uptake into vesicles.

Figure 1. Uptake of FFN206 in cultured cells is dependent on SLC18A1/SLC18A2 activity. FFN206 is able to cross the plasma membrane and selectively accumulates into vesicles through SLC18A1 and SLC18A2.

Assay protocol

HEK-293 JumpIN-SLC18A1 cells were subjected to pharmacological characterization.

Cell preparation

Cells were detached from 80-90% confluent flasks and seeded at 15'000 cells/well in white-transparent bottom PDL-coated 384w plates in medium without the selective antibiotics and incubated 24 hours at 37°C, 5% CO₂. At the same time of seeding cells were induced with 0.5 µg/mL Doxycycline (not induced and mock control in parallel).

FFN206 assay

Medium was removed and Wash Step was performed in Assay buffer (HBSS 1X/20 mM HEPES); the washing steps consist in washing cells 3 times with 80 µL/well of Assay Buffer. Volume left: 20 µL/well.

Then 10 µL/well of Assay Buffer or Tetrabenazine (TBZ, SLC18A2 selective blocker) or Reserpine (SLC18A1 and SLC18A2 blocker) dose-response in Assay Buffer (as 3X; 1% DMSO final concentration) were added and incubated 30 minutes at RT.

Then 10 µL/w (4X) of either FFN206 5 µM (on blocker D/R) or FFN206 D/R (on Assay Buffer, starting from 5 µM; 1:2 dilution step) were incubated 60 minutes at RT.

Wash Step was performed in Assay Buffer (the same as described above).

The fluorescent uptake was measured at Pherastar FSX with excitation and emission wavelengths set at 360 nm and 450 nm respectively (top reading).

Data analysis

Pherastar FSX measurements obtained from different well replicates were analyzed by using the MARS software (BMG Labtech, Version 3.32). Mean and standard deviation of each replicate were

calculated on the exported data with Excel software, then values were used to create sigmoidal dose-response curves (variable slope) and to calculate EC50/IC50 values with GraphPad PRISM software (Version 6).

Additional information

Target data

SLC	SLC18A1
Synonyms	Vesicular Amine Transporter 1, VMAT1
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 18 (Vesicular Monoamine Transporter)
UniProt ID	P54219
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE029C-0 (HEK-SLC18A1-WTOE-p5-6)

Assay data

	Compound name (1)	FFN206
	PubChem CID	137699583
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Tocris, # 5043
	Mode of action	Substrate (analogue)
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC ₅₀ = 2 μM
	Compound name (2)	TBZ
	PubChem CID	6018
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Tocris, # 2175
	Mode of action	Blocker (SLC18A2 specific)
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	IC ₅₀ = na
	Compound name (3)	Reserpine
	PubChem CID	5770

Discussion

The FFN206 assay showed a higher uptake in the SLC18A1 induced cell line, compared to the other conditions. As expected, TBZ, that is selective for SLC18A2, is not active on SLC18A1 while Reserpine inhibits the FFN206 uptake in SLC18A1 induced cells.

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).